

Research Review

Enabling sustainable energy sharing and tracking for rural energy communities in emerging economies

Bokolo Anthony Jnr

Department of Applied Data Science, Institute for Energy Technology, Os Alle 5, Halden 1777, Norway
 Department of Computer Science and Communication, Østfold University College, Halden, Norway

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Rural energy communities
 Peer-to-peer energy trading
 Microgrids
 Energy provenance
 Energy sharing and tracking
 Artificial intelligence
 Smart contracts
 Internet of things
 Distributed ledger technologies

ABSTRACT

Presently Rural Energy Communities (REC) are faced with challenges such as the inefficient distribution of energy from Renewable Energy Sources (RES), unfair pricing, and the inclusion of prosumers into the electricity market. Therefore, this article proposed an approach that employed enabling technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), self-enforcing smart contracts-enabled Internet of Things (IoT), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for sustainable energy sharing and tracking in REC. Additionally, a model is proposed based on key factors that influence the adoption of enabling technologies in REC. For the methodology qualitative data is collected from secondary sources and descriptive analysis is employed to present the key findings. Key findings from this study contributes to develop a decarbonized, decentralized, and digitized energy management approach to support the sustainability of REC. The deployment of AI can facilitate prediction short-term energy planning for RES production and consumption based on real-time data from IoT devices. More importantly, findings from this study presents use case scenarios of energy sharing and tracking, and green electric vehicle charging in REC suggesting that DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI offers an effective approach to accelerate the sharing and tracking of RES in REC. Besides, DLT and smart contracts enables real-time electricity consumption monitoring, energy trading management, and pricing.

Introduction

There is an ongoing development towards the digitalization, decentralization, and decarbonization of energy systems around the world. The diversity of energy producers, including prosumers in Rural Energy Communities (REC) that generates Renewable Energy Sources (RES) are increasing [94], where RES generate clean energy by exploiting natural resources. The integration of RES in REC can contribute to lower peaks when energy demand is high across the community grid, minimize the overall energy consumption, and lessen the disparity in terms of cost and reliability in remote or rural communities [66]. With the increase energy demand and environmental issues, renewable energy from Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) such as small-scale wind turbines, hydro-power, combined heat, and power (CHP), rooftop photovoltaic (PV) solar panels, and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) have gained increasing attention in REC[9]. This is because DERs are more economically efficient and environmentally friendly as compared to traditional fossil energy sources as they produce less pollution and decreases transmission thereby lessening the burden on the power grid [94]. For example, residential buildings with rooftop solar panels can

directly trade surplus energy with nearby neighbors in real-time and get incentivized via a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) approach[48].

Digitalization in the energy domain can contribute to manage associated complexity faced in REC thereby facilitating the production and consumption of renewable energy. But presently there is need for approaches that can support the efficient tracking and tracing of energy produced and consumed in REC[46]. However, research on energy tracing remains scarce. However, it is important to understand the entire end-to-end of electricity generation to consumption to have a positive impact on decarbonization[81]. Most works are mainly focus on the transparency of energy transactions[16]. Also, REC are faced with challenge in engaging prosumers due to lack of dynamic and decentralized policy measures[60,58]. Overcoming this barrier requires future research and practical regulatory design to identify key responsibilities, assets, roles, and models for prosumers in REC. Additionally, there is challenge in designing appropriate local energy market structures for incentivization, and monetization of citizens and municipalities involved in energy sharing and transfer[41]. Mechanisms should be defined for fostering local sustainability, decarbonization, or handling incentives for investing in renewable energy assets at the

E-mail address: anthony.bokolo@ife.no.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ref.2024.100633>

Received 24 July 2024; Received in revised form 27 August 2024; Accepted 4 September 2024

Available online 11 September 2024

1755-0084/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

community level[6]. Generally, the actualization of P2P based energy market necessitates a sophisticated mechanisms involving actors that actively participate in balancing and controlling of the power grid [70,79,94]. Consequently, there is need to ensure proper local electricity market design, pricing schemes, data privacy, security, transparency, and efficiency of energy transactions in REC [70,79,94]. Likewise, prosumers are faced with issues relating to the sharing of renewable energy due to increased complexity[80]. Similarly, achieving energy sharing is very complex due to pluggability, and non-standardization issues faced with the integration and interoperability of different actors, infrastructures, and digital systems leading to silos that do not communicate with each other[69,41].

Enabling technologies such as digital twins, Artificial Intelligence (AI), machine learning, cloud/edge computing, augmented/virtual reality, cyber physical systems, Internet of Things (IoT), Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), etc. can facilitate real-time learning, automation, and decision-making support. The deployment of enabling technologies such as AI, DLT based smart contracts, and IoT can help with the transition of the power grid from a producer-centered and centralized electricity network to a consumer-centric and distributed approach[30]. DLT can provide equitable and auditable information about the source of energy enabling energy provenance or tracking to verify if the energy produced and shared to energy consumers comes from renewable energy sources or not[49]. The features of DLT such as immutability, traceability, transparency, accountability, security, accuracy, etc. enables the real-time tracking of energy from the source of generation, transmission, distribution, and consumption[93]. DLT enables micro transactions in real-time providing transparent access to information for all participants in the electricity network[93]. Likewise, smart contracts enable a more decentralized governance, control, and autonomy to citizens in managing their energy needs towards sustainable energy development in REC[4]. Smart contracts are typically encoded within the DLT platform, and automatically executes transactions depending on pre-specified rules [8].

DLT can be deployed for matching of energy demands from energy supplies based on conditions specified in smart contracts where surplus energy can be traded at transparent prices[4]. DLT and smart contract can support decentralized P2P energy sharing in REC towards creating a completely competitive electricity market for prosumers without relying on the intervention of a centralized governing body, where electricity market participants (energy consumers, prosumers, distributed energy suppliers, Transmission System Operator (TSO), Distribution System Operator (DSO), etc.) can autonomously carryout energy trading based on personal preferences[94]. Furthermore, the deployment of IoT devices such as energy metering devices (Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) and Automated Meter Reading (AMR), etc.), smart energy sensing devices, and intelligent sensors that collects, measures, and transmit energy related data has not only provided opportunities for managing the power grid services but this has also resulted to challenges in managing the generated data [66,3]. Moreover, data generated from energy metering devices can be used by AI based Machine Learning (ML) techniques to extract hidden patterns to effectively devise decision making to manage available energy resources. Using ML techniques, the data can also be used to deploy predictive analytics for energy demand and supply to predict short-term energy demand within REC in order to lessen the delivery cost of electricity for energy consumers [45].

Therefore, this article aims to examine the following research questions.

- How can AI, DLT based smart contracts, and IoT help for orchestrating energy sharing and trading mechanism in REC?
- How can DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI help to achieve sustainable tracking of renewable energy sources in REC?
- What key factors influence the adoption of AI, DLT based smart contracts and IoT in REC?

Accordingly, this study contributes to the literature by examining how the integration of AI, DLT based smart contracts, and IoT enable sustainable energy sharing and tracking in REC. Additionally, this research designs a model based on identified factors that influences the adoption of AI, DLT based smart contracts, and IoT in REC. Findings from this study presents a model that inform and advise decision makers, and stakeholders involved in setting up energy policies on the use of enabling technologies for P2P energy trading and tracking in REC. Also, the purpose of this study is to present an approach that enable intelligent energy sharing and tracking between prosumers and consumers. The presented approach integrates AI, DLT, IoT, and smart contracts enabling day-ahead RES generation, controlling loads, and scheduling supply of RES in order to meet the load demand across the micro grid. The approach can be used to develop and implement a decentralized energy trading platform which enables energy market participants (energy consumers, prosumers, distributed energy suppliers, TSO, DSO, etc.), in REC to operate the electricity network and manage their profile to carryout energy transactions. The remainder of the article is organized as follows: the theoretical background is introduced in Sections 2 and Section 3 is the methodology. The findings are discussed in Section 4. Then the discussion and implications are presented in Section 5. Finally, the conclusion is presented in Section 6.

Theoretical background

Overview of rural energy communities

Several countries have set ambitious targets, such as the increment of the renewable energy share of 32% by 2030 within the European Union [4]. Accordingly, in European countries non-profit associations, local authorities, citizens, and small and medium businesses are cooperating to form energy communities termed as "rural energy communities" that promoted the environmental, economic, and social dimensions of sustainability[35,10]. Rural communities hold great potential because of the space available to initiate renewable energy initiatives. As such there is now a substantial role allotted to energy communities to contribute towards increasing the production and consumption of renewable energy, thus enabling cities and communities to become independent from fossil-based energy[13,35].

As such REC can implement local sustainability projects aimed at reducing energy poverty, driving energy independence, and lessening carbon emissions, as well as creating local jobs[18]. REC utilize physical hardware such as the deployment of IoT sensors and software systems for data analysis and decision making to support the traditional or legacy energy supply systems[85]. REC aim to achieve sustainable polices as summarized in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 1 rural energy communities are local communities that contributes towards the development of sustainable energy cities and communities by supporting prosumers, producers, consumers, citizens, suppliers, authorities, and other actors to set up and manage sustainable energy production and consumption [35]. The consumption of renewable energy has been widely acknowledged as the optimum approach to attain energy sustainability in RES as it greatly enhances the energy consumption efficiency[42]. REC employs distributed power generation infrastructure that provides clean energy for use in a decentralized manner. REC uses distributed generation such as wind, solar, hydropower, and tidal energy for energy supply within small area mostly due to small scale of energy generation and low energy output[86]. Residents in REC are now installing rooftop PV units, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), charging stations for Electric Vehicles (EV) to improve distributed energy performance. Then excess energy generated by home PV systems as well as the energy stored in EV can be feed back to the micro grid to balance the main power grid's energy demand or power stabilization across REC[86].

Fig. 1. Goals of rural energy communities.

Related works and research gap

In REC, regular buildings become active energy suppliers that can share electricity surpluses to the energy market and contribute with their energy capacity to the energy community [13,63]. Besides, citizens and municipalities are becoming interested to know the source of energy they consume to improve their environmental responsibility and prevent rebound effect of carbon emission [74]. However, there is few research on the traceability and tracking of renewable energy power through links of "generation-transmission-transformation-distribution-consumption" to reach citizens and municipalities. But there are claims on utilizing only renewable energy sources to generate electricity [81]. Energy tracing and explainable is important because without a transparent energy footprint, rebound effect of carbon emission and greenwashing may occur [25]. Prior studies such as Petrusic and Janjic [64] proposed a charging system to track the origin of the energy for the charging of EV. Zhang et al. [95] investigated the application of blockchain in renewable energy power scenarios but is mainly concentrated in green certificate transaction scenarios.

Moreover, the current focus in tracing the provenance of electricity remain unclear. This is an important key as things are electrified, it is crucial for citizens and municipalities to know the degree of "greenness" of the electricity source [81]. There is a limited knowledge on community model for energy sharing and transfer designed around the "sharing economy" principles aimed at unlocking the possibility of energy exchange mechanisms for energy communities. This can become increasingly important in the future where electricity information can provide

value for municipalities [74,47]. Another challenge relates to the availability of sufficient energy sharing infrastructure especially for charging EVs in RECs [62,74]. Most EV owners have a car charging facility for their use in REC, which can be either connected to the grid (on-grid) or not (off-grid) to share their charging facilities publicly when they are not using them [34]. There is a limited knowledge regarding privacy rights violation of EV owners and payment model for consumed energy [91]. Thus, charging infrastructure and its management are needed.

Another challenge is a lack of methods and solutions to ensure how electric buses of municipalities and citizens EV fleets can be used to provide on-demand charging to micro-mobilities assets such as e-bikes and e-scooters for V2V in becoming buffers [21,92]. Therefore, new approaches are urgently needed to help the design and marketization of energy flexibilities [89,50]. Thus, it is imperative to consider how enabling technologies such as AI, DLT based smart contracts, and IoT can facilitate energy sharing and encourage participation of EV owners. The deployment of these enabling technologies can help for planning, charging, and discharging scheduling, daily energy demand/generation tracking and tracing, optimization of energy sharing and transfer in REC.

Methodology

In this study a systematic literature review was carryout to synthesize the existing body of research and opted to use google scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science online database, as these platforms provides a source for accessing peer-reviewed scholarly journal articles, conference proceeding, book chapters, books, and technical report documents.

In conducting the review inclusion and exclusion criteria were stipulated to guide the source selection [37,52]. This study is more aligned in literature investigating the factors that influences energy sharing and tracking for REC as well as the adoption of enabling technologies such as DLT, AI, IoT, and smart contracts for energy sharing and tracking in REC. Hence, an organized search was carried out on titles, abstracts, and keywords from the aforementioned online database. The search was conducted within August 2022, and last updated in August 2024.

Different keywords were employed for the searching the online database: “sustainable energy sharing” or “sustainable energy trading” or “energy tracking” and “energy tracing” and “energy provenance*” and “rural energy communities” and “local energy communities*”, and “factors” and “attributes” and “dimensions” and “variables” and “distributed ledger technologies” or “blockchain” or “artificial intelligence” and “machine learning*” and “internet of things *” and “smart contracts” and “big data” and “energy prosumers” and “energy consumers”. The search was limited to only journal articles, conference proceeding, and book chapters, weblinks, technical reports published between the years 2000 and 2024. This study chose to select sources from 2000 as the starting year as rural energy communities research started to pick up from early 2000. All sources were written in English. Fig. 2 depicts the literature search process employed in this study.

The searches resulted in 167 sources respectively as only fewer research have focused on energy sharing and tracking for rural energy communities. Then, 18 papers were excluded as duplicates resulting to 149 sources. The articles titles and abstracts were briefly checked to assess the content of the sources as such 55 sources were excluded as their focus was not fully aligned to the area of energy sharing and tracking for rural energy communities or explored the use of enabling technologies such as DLT, AI, IoT, and smart contracts to support energy sharing and tracking in rural energy communities. Subsequently, the remaining 94 sources were investigated. Also, 2 sources [52]; Fink, 2013), related to literature review were added resulting to a total of 96 sources. Finally, manual coding was carried out and then descriptive analysis is employed to present the key findings from the literature in the subsequent sections.

Findings

Microgrids for stability of rural energy communities

The uncertainty and variability of RES has resulted in challenges in managing the operation of energy systems in REC. Moreover, modern electricity network architectures such as the microgrids are facilitating a central change to distributed energy systems[79]. Therefore, to promote green energy production and consumption, REC are deploying microgrids which are small-scale power generation and distribution infrastructure that comprises of energy storage devices, distributed power sources, energy conversion devices, loads monitoring, and protection devices[86,10]. Microgrids are primarily small-scale self-controllable energy systems that connects with on-site energy generation resources and loads for creating a local balance of energy generation and consumption[94]. Microgrid infrastructures are deployed in REC to help connect electrical facilities in a certain area which then connects with the main power grid that forms an integrated power supply system[93]. Microgrid boosts the survivability and effectiveness of electricity delivery as they are normally connected to an adjoining energy distribution system (i.e., main power grid), enabling them to optimize energy management by not only utilizing on-site resources but actively interacting with the main power grid [7].

Furthermore, microgrid are important in REC in managing decentralized to centralized interconnection from rural to regional power transmission in different zones thereby enhancing the stability of power supply[86,1]. In REC when disruptions such as outages, blackouts or shortages occurs microgrids are isolated from the main power grid and function as a self-sufficient islanded units that sustains and supply critical electricity needed services at an acceptable level[55]. Moreover, microgrids offer flexible solution and highly scalable to improve the operationalization of power grid modernization and also address environmental issues. First, networked microgrids provide a credible means of accommodating distributed energy resources scattered at diverse locations to supplement available resources in individual microgrids[93]. To improve the stability of REC microgrids contribute towards system wide efficacy, security, and safety in energy distribution system as they

Fig. 2. Literature review search process.

effectively respond to dynamic operational conditions triggered by the variability of distributed energy resources outputs [11,48].

Overall, a group of microgrids are innately more reliable than single microgrid, because the connected microgrid provides reserves for their peers to minimize the probability of power shortages or outages within the utility network[55]. Accordingly, microgrids offers an automatic, credible, and auditable approach for maintaining the resilience, efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of the electricity services provided to citizens in REC[55]. The structure of microgrids is based on P2P approach and their inherent distribution of RES suggest that they can contribute to reduce greenhouse gas emission, carbon emissions, and climate change[93]. However, findings from Teng et al. [79] stated that the management of data exchange across different components of micro grids deployed in REC has resulted to more complication in managing energy infrastructures. To enable energy sharing and tracking across microgrids deployed in a housing area with residential buildings (with energy consumers and prosumers), equipped with PV based rooftop panels. Energy metering devices are installed in each building to collect data on energy production and consumption. This data can be used to monitor and forecast energy demand and supply in real time [66].

Energy tracking in rural energy communities

Energy can be generated from different sources, each having its own environmental footprint. In REC residents and companies might be interested in knowing how green the electricity is they are consuming [51]. Likewise, they might be interested in knowing the amount of greenhouse gas emissions they are responsible for when they consume electricity from different sources. Tracing back the origin or source of electricity utilized is evidently a challenging task especially as some quantity of electricity might not be locally produced in REC, since it could be imported from other regions[27]. Electricity cannot be easily tracked along across the electricity distribution network. This is because energy produced, whether from fossil fuel sources or RES is mixed once it is transmitted into the power grid[51]. Additionally, energy tracking can be complicated as energy imported from other regions might be imported from other zones, which sequentially could also be imported from even more distant regions[27].

Typically, the energy tracking lifecycle in REC typically comprises of energy generation, energy transmission, energy transformation, electricity distribution, electricity consumption, and electricity exchange as seen in Fig. 3. Thus, the energy flow-tracing and real-time data of energy produced and transmitted can be employed to trace the provenance of electricity in real-time, even when the electricity is sourced from different energy generation sources (fossil based and RES). Generally,

energy is always produced by power plants such as from solar power stations, wind-based turbines, hydropower plants, etc. After production of the energy the generated electricity from each power plant is mixed. This results to mixed electricity: partly solar-based, hydropower-based, and wind-based energy mix. The quantity of each energy source present within the resulting mix is specified by the share of energy supplied by each contributing power plant. E.g., if a hydropower-based power plant generates twice the energy of a wind-based turbine, then the resulting energy mix is twice that of solar and wind as compared to hydropower-intensive[27]. This energy mix consisting of 50% hydropower, 25% solar, and 25% wind, as shown in Fig. 3.

Accordingly, Fig. 3 shows the proportional mixing and tracking of energy and real-time data flow from different sources (solar, wind, and hydropower), transmitted to be used in REC. Also, the energy mixing process was previously irreversible in traditional energy systems. As such, it is challenging to particularly consume hydropower-based energy once it has been mixed with other energy source. It is only viable to consume energy in proportions that is transmitted from the source where the energy is generated [27]. But recently the use of technologies like virtual power plants and energy attribute certificates (EACs) can enable the tracking and accounting of different energy sources within the grid[73]. Furthermore, Fig. 3 suggest that in the first phase energy is generated from various power plants by utilities and prosumers.

Then real-time data and energy are transmitted via different infrastructure and systems. Next the transmission lines transport the energy at high voltages measured in megawatts (MW), over long distance from power plants. MW or gigawatt (GW) which denotes one billion watts of power is normally used in relation to larger-scale energy generation, such as in a power plant. In the third phase energy is transformed by transformers and then transmitted to substations to be distributed as electricity from transmission lines after being reduced to lower voltages at substations. Then, in the fourth phase the electricity is stepped down by transformers on poles before it is supplied to be consumed by energy consumer in residential areas which is measured in kilowatt (kW). The electricity can also be shared in the case of prosumers within the microgrid for other residents in REC.

Energy tracking approaches in rural energy communities

Future energy systems in REC will be distributed, supported by enabling technologies for bi-directional communication among all entities within the power grid[4]. To track the source of energy a few approaches have been employed in practice such as contract-path tracking approach, book and claim methods such as “guarantees of origin” and “renewable energy certificates” or “the International Renewable Energy Certificates” (I-RECs).[3,51]. The contract-path

Fig. 3. Energy tracking supply chain in rural energy communities.

approach is a conventional method which is applied to verify, track, and trace the chain of ownership of RES from generation to consumption[3]. Renewable energy certificate is a method that uses certificates to track the source of energy. In practice one renewable energy certificate is

equivalent to one megawatt hour (MWh) which also equals 1,000 kilowatts hour (kWh) of energy produced per hour is delivered to the power grid[72,3].

Renewable energy certificate offers a type of renewable energy

Table 1
Comparative review of studies on energy sharing and trading from academic viewpoint.

References	Contributions	Enabling technologies	Explored areas	Methodology employed	Outcome	Countries
Kong et al. [54]	developed an optimization method for sharing energy storage.	Algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Self-sufficiency – Self-consumption – Subjectivity 	Experiment and simulation	Supported distributed generation systems to trade energy and to share energy storage systems.	China
Wu et al. [88]	investigated P2P energy trading optimization.	Algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Prosumers – Carbon emission – Pricing competition 	Experiment and simulation	Focused on community prosumers by considering carbon cap-and-trade.	China
Sousa et al. [75]	designed an optimal design for renewable energy communities.	Algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Self-consumption – Investment decisions – Optimization 	Experiment and simulation	Provided an optimization model for investment in wind/PV capacity in RES sharing.	Portugal
Zhou and Lund [96]	designed a P2P energy sharing and trading for RES in smart communities.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Trading pricing – Decision-making – Multi-stakeholders 	Literature review	Presented trading pricing models, decision-making and collaboration.	China and Finland
Xia et al. [90]	proposed a pricing mechanism for P2P energy sharing market diffusion.	AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Dynamic network usage price 	Experiment and simulation	Established the cost minimization to analyze market equilibrium in hybrid P2P energy market.	United States of America (USA) and China
Minuto and Lanzini [59]	researched on energy sharing mechanisms for energy.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sharing mechanism – Load demand – Virtual net-metering 	Experiment and simulation	Focused on members based on different user demand profiles and asset ownership schemes.	Italy
Jamil et al. [45]	designed a P2P power trading approach based for sustainable energy supply in smart grid.	AI and Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Energy trading – Energy prediction – Predictive analysis 	Experiment and simulation	Aimed to achieve optimum energy flow and energy crowdsourcing, aiding energy trading among energy consumer and prosumer.	South Korea
Schneiders and Shipworth [71]	explored P2P energy trading communities.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Energy communities – Energy trading – Transactive energy 	Literature review	Assess if the legal forms available to energy communities can help resolve uncertainties in P2P energy trading.	United Kingdom (UK)
Yagmur et al. [91]	provided a Distribution System Operator (DSO) view for energy systems.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Smart grid – DERs – AMI 	Literature review	Defined the DSO-based requirements for systems within the energy sector mainly EV.	Turkey, South Korea, and Oman
Zhang et al. [94]	developed a P2P energy trading in a microgrid.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Microgrid – P2P energy trading – Iterative double auction 	Experiment and simulation	Employed a mechanism that enables buyers and sellers adjust quotes based on the market equilibrium price.	China and USA
Aderibole et al. [3]	investigated smart grids and a decentralized model.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Smart grid – Decentralization – Trust and incentive 	Literature review	Provided a reference architecture based on the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) framework.	USA, United Arab Emirates (UAE), and Egypt
Aloqaily et al. [5]	presented an energy trade framework.	Blockchain and smart contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Distributed trading – Distributed resources – P2P energy trading 	Literature review	Provided best practices for sustainable energy and benefits of technologies in the energy sector.	UAE, Canada, and Pakistan
Duan [31]	presented an intelligent energy buy and trade platform.	IoT and blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Intelligent contract – Electric coin 	Literature review	Aimed to address security measures to avoid the impact of electricity surge or reduction on the grid.	China
Seven et al. [73]	designed a P2P energy trading for virtual power plant.	Blockchain and smart contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Bidding system – Ethereum 	Experiment and simulation	Presented a scheme for auction to address cost and security concerns.	Turkey, China, and Australia
Ahl et al. [4]	designed an analytical framework for P2P microgrids.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Microgrid – Peer-to-peer – Renewable energy 	Literature review and Interviews	Researched on blockchain-based distributed energy for institutional development.	Japan, Hong Kong, and UK
Ferrag and Maglaras [36]	developed DeepCoin for energy exchange method in smart grids.	AI and Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Machine learning – Smart grid – Security 	Experiment and simulation	Provided a deep learning-based and blockchain scheme for reliable P2P energy system.	Algeria and UK
Jain and Dogra [44]	explored the distribution of solar energy.	Blockchain and IoT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Decentralization – Cryptocurrency 	Literature review	Enable solar panels to charge the battery connected to microcontroller.	India
Li et al. [55]	decentralized transactive energy management system.	Blockchain and smart contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Networked microgrids – Transactive energy – Energy management 	Simulation	Provided a scheme for networked microgrids to optimize the operations of energy distribution systems.	USA
Wang et al. [84]	explored energy trading in electrical power system.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Energy trading – Electrical power system 	Literature review	Identified the challenges faced in blockchain-based energy trading.	China, USA, and Qatar
Kodali et al. [53]	studied on energy trading.	Blockchain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Renewable electricity generation 	Literature review	Provided a P2P energy transacting network that accommodate RES.	India

currency which can be exchanged for cash and based on the value of these certificates which typically fluctuates based on the current market conditions [51]. The I-RECs approach enables industries to track the consumption of clean energy beyond North America and Europe whereas the guarantees of origin method make it likely for energy consumers to claim a precise amount and type of renewable energy as theirs. These approaches use a database where energy producers and prosumers can book or register how much, how, and when the energy has been produced. Energy consumers can claim the use of clean electricity grounded on this information. For this Energy Attribute Certificates (EACs) are issued to prosumers, suppliers, and consumers as proof of a renewable energy purchase [93].

Also, other approaches include the use of tracking systems which aims to keep the end users such as the consumers and prosumers informed and to prevent duplicate counting when the generated energy is transmitted through the power grid[94]. In REC prevention of double counting is vital to guarantee that no other energy consumer claims to use the same clean energy as another. Across the European landscape, tracking certificates referred to as Guarantees of Origin as previously stated are managed by the Domestic GO registries are coordinated by state-appointed bodies such as energy regulators or power grid operators [91].

In countries such as Canada and in the United States of America, electricity tracking certificates are referred to as renewable electricity certificates which are used both in compliance markets and the voluntary carbon market. The ownership of these renewable electricity certificates is required for actors to claim the consumption of RES. Another non-profit organization in Finland is EKOenergy which supports the use of tracking certificates for tracing where the energy has been produced within the same electricity market. The EKOenergy standards states that the energy consumer must always be notified about the country of origin of the procured energy[33].

Comparative review on energy sharing and trading

Presently digitalization in REC has resulted to setbacks in managing the over increasing amount of data as well as security issues that has risen due to a single point of failure[4]. This has risen to difficulty as the data complexity surges[4]. To this end a few studies have contributed to address these aforementioned issues in improving energy sharing and trading from the academic viewpoint in Table 1. But none of the studies employed DLT, AI, IoT, and smart contracts to improve energy sharing and tracking in REC. Also, issues related to the efficient distribution of energy from RES, unfair pricing, and the inclusion of prosumers into the electricity market has not been well researched in the literature.

Application of DLT based smart contracts, IoT and AI for energy tracking

The electricity grid comprises of a network which includes power plants and power lines spanning across several areas. The electricity network comprises of zones with areas within which the electricity is presumed to freely flow without any restrictions[93]. These supposed zones can symbolize states, countries, or even islands, in relation to the availability of data. Energy generated from power plants can flow between different zones via so-called interconnectors, which denote the exports and the imports of energy between neighboring zones[94]. The constrained capacity of the interconnector enforces restrictions on how much electricity can be transmitted to and from a neighboring zone[27]. Furthermore, the tracking of energy throughout the supply chain requires using sensitive data which needs to be regulated between different actors in REC. As such data privacy, security, and transparency should be taken into consideration[91]. Enabling technologies such as DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI can be employed to track energy in different zones or across zones within REC as seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 illustrates how DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI can be employed to track and verify the source of energy generated, consumed, and shared in REC. DLT is a decentralized data storage that can enable data sharing, replication, and synchronization across a network of multiple node users. In comparison to traditional storage systems, DLT employs consensus mechanism and utilizes multi-party decision-making as well as a common maintenance procedure for data storage and replication [86]. Whereas the traditional data storage systems are typically based on a data management mechanism managed by a central authority[85]. DLT is suitable as it provides a digital record-keeping mechanism using cryptography to protect the sharing of highly sensitive data. DLT creates complete, tamperproof, transparent, history for data and transaction flow by providing a secure end-to-end information visibility across the energy supply chain using a decentralized shared ledger as a source of truth [51].

DLT can be used to directly verify if energy purchased by a consumer is certainly from a specific renewable source by offering a visual time-stamped traceable link of energy supply from specific source(s) for both the energy producers, prosumers, and consumers for traceability of energy right from its source all the way to the energy consumer[15]. DLT uses time-stamped log for tracking asset's location and status at any point in time thereby replacing manual process and improving traceability for achieving proof of origin functionality for consumers of the services such as RES (Anthony Jnr, 2020). Moreover, DLT can be used to store data related to green energy certificates linked to a prosumer who produce energy from RES. This certificate is mostly issued by the government based on the specific amount of green energy, thus supporting prosumers to produce green energy[5]. The IoT was a term used to

Fig. 4. DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI for energy tracking in rural energy communities.

describe an infrastructure where the internet enables connectivity with real or physical things such as sensors that generates and transmits data via a ubiquitous network as first reported by Kevin Ashton in 1999[14]. Since then, the IoT has been promoting the digital transformation energy systems in cities and communities.

In REC IoTs such as energy metering devices help prosumers and consumers to rate, store, trade, and purchase electricity. bring more intelligence and flexibility into new generation of future energy systems [86]. In REC IoT infrastructure are being deployed one of which are the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) and Automated Meter Reading (AMR) technology that supports the bi-directionally transmission of information between energy consumers, prosumers, and the utility (actor responsible to sell the energy) [3]. For example, AMI enable remote meter reading, prepaid energy services, and demand-side management[3]. Generally, AMI provides high level metering, measurement, and monitoring that allow extensive communication among different actors within the micro grid[91]. Also, employing IoT devices such as energy metering devices, smart sensors, intelligent electronic devices, circuit breakers, capacitor banks, advanced metering infrastructures, etc. installed at strategic locations along the energy supply chain autonomously record the energy's journey. The use of IoT devices routinely collects energy related data (e.g., location, quantity, time, type, etc.), and then transmits these data to the DLT platform to ensure traceability as the asset (energy) moves via the supply chain[91].

Data sharing is required to improve the efficiency of demand response and better management of energy assets in REC towards contributing to a low-carbon, green energy systems[66,79]. But REC are faced with the management of real-time data generated from energy metering devices and intelligent sensors which are utilized as information for decision making support[5]. AI based ML can greatly enhance the prediction accuracy of RES output, curtail voltage fluctuation, and promote the consumption of green renewable energy [86]. In addition, AI based algorithms are needed to ascertain the optimal aggregate of electricity represented by a token in kilowatt. Overall, the AI based algorithms comprise of parameters, such as the number of consumers and prosumers[32], the quantity of energy made available to be traded, the quantity of energy available for sharing, the transaction history, energy demand, energy consumption forecast and weather conditions[5]. Likewise, analyses of real-time data or historical data with ML algorithm can help for planning of energy generation and forecasting of energy demand, accordingly, using processed data in making strategic decisions for renewable energy generation, sustainable energy storage, reliability of the electricity market, transparent pricing, energy tracking, and standardization of regulations and policies[94]. AI can support real-time loads scheduling based on system generation, demands, and precising. AI analyze the generated data from IoT devices for forecasting energy demand and supply[45].

The use of the IoT devices with AI enable prosumers and utility companies to predict the daily demand profile of consumers based on the energy consumption data gathered from energy metering devices such as AMI and AMR. In addition, the real-time data produced from IoT devices can be employed to digitally verify, the production of green energy certificates stored within the distributed ledger (Jnr et al., 2021). Also, this data comprises of the energy producer, source, quantity produced, and the timeframe. This token will be stored in the DLT will capture the hour-by-hour produced energy that can be used for energy tracking and tracing in REC [51]. The collected data can be made available to relevant parties (e.g., TSO, DSO, auditors, prosumers, producers, government agencies, consumers, suppliers, etc.) in issuing green energy certificates to ensure sustainable production and consumption in REC[93]. By using the green energy certificates a prosumer, producer, or supplier can be linked to a RES based on a unique digital energy identifier or token created and stored in the DLT. Accordingly, smart contracts can be used to enable the tracking and tracing green energy certificates offering an energy chain that guarantees periodical metering for energy consumers on the DLT[45]. Also, the authenticity of

the energy related data can be verified by the smart contract which offers expandability possibilities for example P2P energy sharing and trading in REC. This information provides transparency in accordance with sustainability measures on the provenance of the generated energy for all actors involved in providing green energy certificates[9].

Integrating DLT, smart contracts, and IoT for energy sharing

Traditionally energy is transferred to consumers via long transmission lines, and since the power flows through the grids constantly much of it is wasted. A DLT based platform can be deployed to increase the effectiveness and minimize the costs of supply companies and retailers by enabling consumers to directly connect to prosumers and the wholesale markets[5]. Economically, DLT-enabled power operation can efficiently adjust electricity prices thereby reducing the need for long-distance transmission loss[79]. Thus, DLT enables energy sharing and trading using tokenization of the asset (electricity), whereby tokens are utilized to specify that a specific quantity of energy was produced from a RES, which is transferred from a prosumer to consumers using the DLT based platform[28]. Thus, Table 2 reviews industrial use cases on the application DLT for energy sharing. However, only fewer studies employed AI and IoT for energy sharing in REC from the practitioner's viewpoint.

Findings from Table 2 indicates that DLT can be deployed to support point-to-point electricity sharing among citizens in REC. Evidence from the literature reveal that studies that employed AI and IoT in conjunction with DLT from the industrial perspective are sparse, as such there is need for research that explored this gap in knowledge. The is important as the use of DLT, AI and IoT can supports energy consumers to access relevant data such as energy generation, energy consumption and other energy related information in real-time through energy metering devices [45]. This enables a participatory market-driven environment where consumers can completely order and complete electricity transactions without contacting a utility company realized via a series of transaction protocols[86]. The use of the token or termed as tokenizing improves energy exchanges between suppliers and consumers[5]. In such approach a token is produced for each amount of renewable energy in kilowatt, which is then stored or sold to consumers and wholesale markets across the DLT based platform. By exchanging or trading tokens energy consumers can purchase energy from prosumers or wholesale market in exchange for energy at a lower cost as compared to buying energy from conventional energy suppliers[78]. The token can also be transferred or sold to other consumers who can later sell these tokens when their market value increases, thus creating a revenue stream. Tokens can be used to incentivize and track consumers of RES in order to promote its consumption in REC[5].

Furthermore, smart contracts can programmatically define the appropriate incentives or charges needed to incentivize prosumers, and rules needed for the community grid to balance energy production and energy demand[79]. The use of smart contracts promotes a higher level of automation for the DLT platform that connects energy generators and energy consumers to meeting the needs of environmentally friendly and low-carbon supply that favor clean and green energy[86]. Smart contracts help for real-time reward scheme, day-ahead energy scheduling, short-term energy prediction, and long-term energy prediction by capturing information on deployed assets, participants, and transactions [45]. DLT enables energy consumers and prosumers to use their smart phones to issue smart contracts linked to their residential energy metering device. Based on the rules of the smart contract, the energy metering devices are linked to the community grid to support energy sharing, trading, and supply. In REC this enables an open, democratic, and inclusive energy eco-system that utilizes the elements of existing power grid technology with DLT to improve the existing energy infrastructure to increase energy efficiency and independence[86]. To this end P2P energy trading employing DLT, such as blockchain is a potential

Table 2
Industrial perspective on DLT application for energy sharing

References	Contributions	DLT deployed	Energy domain	Outcome	Countries
NRGcoin [61]	Developed an open-source energy trading platform that utilizes individual renewable energy.	Crypto-currency (NRGcoin)	Renewable energy	Provided a virtual crypto-currency that can be easily changeable with euros.	Belgium
Schneiders and Shipworth [71]	Reported on P2P energy trading which are being tested in the energy regulatory sandbox framework (Ofgem).	Blockchain	Renewable energy	Focused to test energy innovations without the regulatory requirements that typically applies.	UK
Sunchain [77]	Project provided virtual network assistance for solar energy prosumers to share surplus solar energy.	Hyperledger Fabric	Solar energy sharing	Aimed to improve energy transactions at a minimum cost and also traces the absolute trail of energy generation and sharing.	France
Quartierstrom [68]	Is a lighthouse P2P energy community initiative.	Blockchain	Solar energy sharing	Aimed that locally generated electricity should be locally utilized.	Switzerland
Ableitner et al. [2]	Reported on the repowering program a not-for-profit organization that facilitates community energy initiative.	Blockchain	Renewable energy	Aimed at testing a local P2P energy trading platform.	UK
Mengelkamp et al. [57], Brooklyn Microgrid [20]	Reported on the design of the Brooklyn microgrid for energy markets.	Ethereum	Solar energy sharing	Aimed to build an automatic and safe P2P transaction and payment network between residents in Brooklyn.	USA
Cityxchange [26]	Developed a positive energy building and districts for electricity supply network.	IOTA tangle	Solar energy sharing	Focused to achieve energy reduction and efficiency, local RES storage, flexibility, electric mobility, and P2P energy trading.	Norway and Ireland
Goierer [39]	Developed an energy cooperative to provide consumers with a choice of RES, including energy produced by prosumers.	Blockchain (Pylon Network)	Renewable energy	Offered a form of P2P energy trading provided to as a service to community members.	Spain
Powerledger [67], Hall [40]	Reported on Power Ledger a platform that bring flexibility and resilience to power grids.	Blockchain	Solar energy sharing	Focused to provide markets that remove the barriers to interrupted renewable energy.	Australia

application to this issue, since it can enable the balancing of energy supply with demand at a local level to facilitate the use of clean energy [71].

Using connected IoT devices such as energy metering devices the generated energy and consumed electricity is measured and recorded in the blockchain platform. Based on data collected from the energy metering devices, the blockchain platform matches sellers and buyers of RES and smart contracts accordingly settles the fiscal transactions between the participants [71]. The adoption of smart metering devices and energy storage systems such as Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) with capacity defined can further accelerate the integration prosumers into the community grid in REC. However, the intermittent injection of renewable energy into the power grid by prosumers has been difficult to manage. This is because the power grids are not deployed to absorb surplus energy input, such as the energy produced by solar PV systems [94]. In REC most power grids are mostly designed to support unidirectional flow of energy to consumers from generators. The bidirectional energy flow from prosumers feeding energy into the power grid can cause disruption resulting to extra costs for energy consumers, because of the increased electricity network management carried out by centralized grid participants [45]. Overall DLT offers several opportunities to improve REC operations such as enabling P2P energy trading, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) management where EV are used for dynamic energy storage, renewable energy certificates, and ancillary services [4].

Deployment of DLT for seamless electric vehicle charging in REC

The increased spotlight on lessening CO₂ emission in cities and communities has resulted to the proliferation of EV. Where an EV is referred to as a vehicle that is powered by at least one electric motor [3]; Anthony Jnr, 2020). Although in REC EV supports the transportation of citizens it can also be used for storing and supplying energy during off-peak and when peak demand is high. Findings from the literature suggest that by 2035 at least 50 percent of newly bought cars in Europe will be electric. Taking into account such an unprecedented increment in energy demand by EVs, the forecasting of energy loads for EVs will be challenging [3]. As such researchers such as Wang et al. [84] highlighted that renewable energy can be provided for the charging operation of EVs

during the day, while in the night central battery pack that stores excess energy can be used to minimize the charging cost for EV owners in REC.

While most EV owners have their privately owned charging unit which can be either be on-grid (connected to the grid) or off-grid (not connected to the grid). There is need for research on the impact of EV charging on the micro grid as during peak hours DSOs are faced with system robustness issues and the management of peak load in REC [9,91]. Evidence from the literature [91] argued that DLT can support the interaction of EV charging with the micro grid in REC. Accordingly, Fig. 5 presented some of the fundamental benefits of employing DLT for seamless EV charging in REC. As illustrated in Fig. 5 DLT can support charging operations in REC. Other benefits of employing DLT for EV charging includes the dynamic collection of energy consumption/production data, improves grid efficiency, adjustment of peak demand, improves grid stability, and sustainable energy sharing and trading [91].

Factors that impact adoption of enabling technologies in REC

The adoption of enabling technologies such as AI, DLT based smart contracts and IoT in REC is influenced by different factors as these technologies are still emerging topics in the energy sector. Ground on prior work by Ahl et al. [4] the model explore how emerging technologies are influenced by community readiness as well as understanding the sustainability aspects based on economic, social, and environmental variables. Overall, the conceptualized model factors comprise of institutional, technological, economic, social, and environmental as seen in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 shows the designed model for investigating the factors that influences the adoption of enabling technologies in REC for emerging economies. Each of the factors and derived proposition are discussed below.

Institutional

Uncertainty of roles of some actors in the distributed ledger, and legal uncertainty associated with the lack of standardization, unclear identities, and obligations on the electricity markets and difficulty in settling dispute especially in emerging economies [5]. As such in

Fig. 5. Key benefits of employing DLT for seamless EV charging in REC.

Fig. 6. Designed conceptual model for enabling technologies adoption in REC.

achieving full scale P2P-trading here is need for complete regulatory change for energy sharing and tracking in the future. Licensing of prosumers and GDPR issues related to data privacy, ownership, and sovereignty is still a challenge[38]. Based on the GDPR, residents have the

right to request for their data to be deleted and to have sovereignty on the use of their data. But this opposes the immutability nature of DLTs such as blockchain[4]. Overall, several institutional issues were emphasized varying from uncertainty and complex regulatory process

involved in deploying DLT, cryptocurrency taxation, and existing energy market polices in emerging economies. Similarly, evidence from Ahl et al. [4] mentioned that double surcharge of network fees and tax for battery charging and discharging is seen as a challenge for grid flexibility. Also, the use of DLT in REC within emerging economies is faced with governance issue pertaining to who will manage and maintain the DLT platform [10]. Based on the proceeding argument, the following proposition is suggested:

P1. The institutional strategies initiated will significantly influence the adoption of enabling technologies in REC.

Technological

Technological decisions are needed at the inception of new energy related initiative. Findings from domain experts revealed that technologies such as DLT and smart contracts are crucial in the energy sector and use of these technologies may change over time in emerging economies. As DLT is not a panacea emerging in isolation but is probable a constituent of a toolbox alongside other technologies, such as AI and IoT [4]. Also, the use of these technologies is faced with issues such privacy and data security, lack of rollout for smart metering devices, interoperability and hardware integration of existing and future systems to reduce data silos in emerging economies (Anthony [47]). Also, other issues relate to the availability of large-scale data storage, scalability in terms of Throughput Per Second (TPS), and latency in terms of in terms of Round-Trip Time (RTT) and Server Processing Time (SPT) especially for DLT such as blockchain (Anthony Jnr, 2024c). Accordingly, the following proposition is stated:

P2. Technological issues addressed in the society will significantly impact the use of enabling technologies in REC.

Economic

The use of enabling technologies such as DLT are influencing utilities in terms of initiating new business models, actors and specifying roles within the micro grid[31]. This variable includes existing electricity market mechanisms, market interoperability and incentivization and pricing mechanism to be employed using DLT and smart contracts[4]. Also, there are unclear mechanism on how smart contracts can help to settle disputes when sharing energy in REC within emerging economies. This further considers how capital-intensive the role of prosumers is in microgrid development, the non-dynamic inflexibility mechanisms, and high transaction costs associated in running the electricity market[44]. Moreover, there are issues related to investment risk and uncertainty in prosumer business models orchestrated by smart contracts, and possibility of gaining financial returns on digital solutions in emerging economies. There is also challenge with associated community grid development expenses[38]. Evidence from the literature suggest that associated operational costs such as brokerage fees may discourage small scale prosumers[4]. Based on the above-mentioned discussion the following proposition is presented:

P3. The current economic policies initiated will significantly influence the adoption of enabling technologies in REC.

Social

The use of enabling technologies in REC may have substantial impacts on the existing, social infrastructure, societal values, and corporate business models, as such there is need for potential changes of norm [55]. For example, when previous energy consumers also become prosumers, they may feel more engaged and in so doing they become invested in the community energy strategies in emerging economies[4]. Several researchers emphasized the significance of stakeholder interest management in the incentivization and marketization of the microgrid in emerging economies (Anthony [48]). The social challenges include disruption caused by decentralized technologies regarding some actors

being removed from their roles and jobs, and conservatism from incumbent utilities. Also, findings from the literature suggested that inadequate digital skills and user-friendliness on the application of AI and DLT has resulted to low acceptance and community participation and engagement[4]. But user engagement and involvement are key considerations with the increasing digitalization of the energy sector in emerging economies. Thus, there is need for proper communication strategies to boost stakeholders' involvement [12]. It is also suggested that co-creation, participatory planning, and community-building can be employed to facilitate multiple stakeholders involved in energy sharing and trading operations in REC within emerging economies[4]. Based on the findings from the literature, the following proposition is made:

P4. Current social practice in the community level will significantly influence the adoption of enabling technologies in REC.

Environmental

Energy systems of today are progressively being digitalized, thus incorporating environmental regulations and zero or low carbon technologies in REC may contribute to environmental sustainability in emerging economies. This has resulted to issues which include how to improve energy management and self-sufficiency technologies for environmentalism[4]. Although the adoption of enabling technologies such as DLT can contribute to reduce CO₂ emissions by enabling transparency in energy trading, traceability of renewable energy. There is still need of new regulations for trading of RES in REC within emerging economies [10]. For example, the sharing of renewable energy certificate sales for prosumers who produce solar energy in REC is not legally approved for trading in some countries. Additional issues highlighted in the literature involves associated costs of renewable energy infrastructures, fraud cases related to renewable energy certificates, and high resources needed for deploying DLT based platforms[4]. Moreover, the use of these technologies requires high energy consumption when renewable energy is used contributes to CO₂ emissions [66]. Thus, there is need for environmentally friendly and energy efficient technologies to be deployed in REC within emerging economies. Hence, as discussed this proposition is stated:

P5. Environmental target stipulated by government bodies will significantly influence the adoption of enabling technologies in REC.

Economic model for REC in emerging economies

Findings from the literature revealed that a few studies that designed economic model underlying the energy sharing platform. Among these studies Chau et al. [22] designed an effective cost-sharing mechanisms for Peer-to-peer energy sharing. Chen et al. [24] presented an energy sharing game based on a generalized demand bidding approach. Likewise, Pires Klein et al. [65] proposed a business model for peer-to-peer energy sharing in energy market. Wang et al. [82] developed an incentive mechanism that enables the sharing DER. Also, Wang et al. [83] provided an energy sharing scheme and mechanism design to incentivize DER aggregation in energy markets. Srikanth et al. [76] proposed a prosumer driven economic model to support energy sharing across microgrids in a rural scenario. Additionally, Wang et al. [87] designed a two-level incentive mechanism for peer-to-peer energy sharing. Chen and Zhao [23] reviewed energy sharing and identifies existing business models and mechanisms. Zhou and Lund [96] presented a trading pricing models for peer-to-peer energy sharing and trading of RES in smart communities.

Grounded on the literature[76], an economic model is adapted and applied to the REC context in emerging economies. where prosumers are connected to the microgrid in REC to facilitate and contributes to energy sharing with other residents connected to the community microgrids and is rewarded with economic benefits. This proposed economic model is different from the traditional economic model, as several stakeholders

can be involved enabling energy consumers to benefit from improved performance and lower power expense. Therefore, the economic model provides commercial value where the energy tariff is fixed to a certain Kilowatt-hour (*kWh*) based on the current energy spot price in the local energy market regardless of where the energy is being produced, supplied or consumed. Each prosumer is rewarded for the electricity produced that is supplied and consumed by energy consumers (*Cr*) in the community microgrids and its commercial equivalent is labelled as the estimated income. Likewise, energy consumers or prosumers are also billed for the total electricity they consume including the imported energy from other entities (*Dr*) and the monetary value of this energy is estimated as an expense. The overall business model highlighting the “net Expense or Income” is denoted as (*Expr*) of a given prosumer with a REC is denoted using the equation below:

$$Expr = Cr * T - Dr * T$$

Expr = Estimated_Revenue – Estimated_Expense

Where, *Expr* = Total Revenue Stream to entity *r*

Cr = Total available energy produced by a prosumer *r*

Dr = Total Electricity utilized by individuals (energy consumers and prosumers) *r*

T = Fixed Electricity Tariff Rate in community microgrids across REC

Overall, in the economic model positive value represents profit to the prosumer, whereas negative value indicates expense for the energy consumer or prosumer[76].

Findings from use case scenarios

The infusion of enabling technologies in RES can improve grid flexibility, improve reliability, and decrease operating costs. As such, the adoption of enabling technologies such as DLT in the REC can facilitate distributed energy trading marketplace towards the actualization of a future zero-carbon sustainable communities. Likewise, the use of IoT devices such as advanced intelligent metering devices can produce data on electricity, and the use of AI based machine learning for big data analysis can support to optimize the management of energy resources and improve electricity utilization. But presently, most studies that applied DLT such as blockchain for energy systems are predominantly in the form of pilot developments, which are faced with several challenges on how to manage cost and control scalability while maintaining security as well as data privacy issues [4,5]. Thus, there is a need of practical use cases discussion on how to address these aforementioned challenges [4]. Therefore, this section presents two possible use case scenarios which comprises of energy sharing and tracking, and green EV charging in REC.

Use case scenario on energy sharing and tracking in REC

Prosumers can be residential buildings that are adapted for producing renewable energy, as well as EVs that share and feed energy back to the power grid and, similarly, energy consumers can be both EVs and residents of a housing community that utilizes energy as a service. REC which are large scale rural communities can be integrated into the process of generating or consuming energy, and an aggregator can be deployed between the participants (energy consumers and prosumers), and the micro grid can help coordinator electricity demand and supply [5]. By employing a DLT based approach a prosumer provides energy to be traded into the power grid through an aggregator, and then the aggregator or an energy router broadcasts the electricity sale offers (via smart contracts), for all prosumers to the network nodes. Prosumer maintains the energy generation data collected from the PV solar panel and then records the amount of energy generated into the DLT platform.

The energy consumer can get available renewable energy from the local electricity market by sending a query request in the DLT[45]. To buy energy, the consumer executes energy procurement transaction, and the battery energy storage systems transfers the matching energy to the consumer. Once the demanded energy is successfully transferred to the consumer, smart contract initiated the payment by converting the

transferred energy into cryptocurrency in coins. After the energy transaction is verified by a miner node that execute validation and publishing of transactions on the distributed ledger, the energy transactions are recorded in the distributed ledger[5]. Next, the payment is credited to the digital wallet of the prosumer and a confirmation is sent to the utility (responsible to sell the energy), and prosumer[45]. Energy consumer can access and read available renewable energy offers, and if any meets its conditions, the user sends a purchase request with the payment to the prosumer. The transaction request is made available to both parties after verification and is saved within the DLT and a confirmation message is then routed to the aggregator to release and supply the electricity to the consumer [5].

An energy consumer can request for verification to know the source of the energy being consumed and the DLT system can provide information on the traceability of the energy based on the available green energy certificate if available. For example, considering energy generated from PV solar panels, energy related data are collected through intelligent sensors installed on PV panels on the kw of production and storage. This data is then transmitted to the DLT system which then invokes the smart contracts that intelligently issues the corresponding green energy certificates for prosumers and producers to get economic incentives for every kw of clean energy generated[79]. Thus, energy producers or prosumers deploy energy metering devices that is connected to the DLT system as this help for monitoring and coordination energy generation, supply, and demand from consumers in their local neighborhood. AI and smart contract are also employed for dynamic pricing and optimizing decision-making for electricity market participants[79].

Use case scenario on green EV charging in REC

Using DLT EV owners can easily access locations of available EV charging stations on the map and automatically confirm their identity. When an EV user wants to charge an EV, the user can use the DApp to find nearby available charging station. DLT enables the charging and electricity pricing optimization process to be completely traceable thus improve transparency and trust on cost, source, and type of electricity being consumed[86]. Smart contract can then complete the payment verification process for charging charges based an electronic wallet provided for processing of charging fees associated with agreements with the EV owner and charging station provider who supplies renewable energy for charging thereby increasing the use of clean energy. With this approach there is no need for EV owners to sign any power supply contract or subscribe to any energy company. They can use the decentralized application (DApp) installed in their smartphone to complete user authentication and charging. The DApp is typically a platform that can autonomously be operated through the use of smart contracts deployed on a DLT.

In this scenario the price of the electricity is automatically computed via a third part application (such as Nord Pool, European Energy Exchange AG (EEX), European Power Exchange, California Independent System Operator, Australian Energy Market Operator, etc.), via RESTful Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) protocol to manage user requests [45], and provides data in real-time according to the local grid load condition. This helps to provide accessible clean energy for charging EV, enable sharing of charging piles, and seamless payment for charging EV. Additionally, with the connection of DLT with smart meters and intelligent sensors deployed in EVs, the energy consumed for charging as G2V, transmitted via V2G to be consumed and Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) is recorded into the distributed ledger. As such all-energy related data collected and stored in the DLT is transparent, authenticated, and traceable. DLT can efficiently ensure that the integrity of metering data that records the amount of energy used by the EV and associated billing records are immutable, and it can also support to preserve the privacy of EV owners' identity. In practice, conventional energy metering and invoicing often require extra management costs, as such are faced with mistakes and even frauds. But with the use of smart contracts, advanced metering

infrastructure, and automated meter reading technology billing can be automated and as such administrative cost of needed for metering and billing can be reduced, and the likelihood of frauds and mistakes can also be minimized[86].

Discussion and implications

Discussion

In emerging economies access to clean energy based on solar, wind, etc. is often the optimal way to electrify rural or local regions as these energy sources are cheaper than centralized power plant and power grid extensions. Evidence from the literature reported a yearly growth rate for RES trading market predicting an increase of at least 10 % in the coming years[5]. Through the incorporation of micro grids, local renewable energy generation, supply and demand are better optimized and balanced which also facilitates the penetration of larger volumes of RES in REC. However, the management and operation of energy systems have become much challenging due to the involvement of different actors leading to the need for advanced technologies and data exchange in REC. This has prompted the adoption of enabling technologies such as DLT based smart contracts, AI, and IoT. These technologies are deployed for distributed energy production, consumption, and transactions of renewable energy in REC[70]. The impact of enabling technologies on sustainable energy development in REC still needs further study. Accordingly, findings from this study indicates that the adoption of enabling technologies in REC is faced with many issues, ranging from institutional, technological, economic, social, and environmental factors as seen in Fig. 6.

Therefore, this study aims to develop a decarbonized, decentralized, and digitized energy management approach to support the sustainability of REC by designing a model based on key factors that influence the adoption of enabling technologies to enable the sharing and tracking of energy in REC. Additionally, an approach is proposed that employed DLT based smart contracts, IoT and AI for sustainable energy sharing and tracking electricity transactions across REC. The developed approaches will contribute to achieve a fair sharing and tracking of energy towards a democratic, decentralized, inclusive, and transparent energy management system. Accordingly, the use of enabling technologies is considered enablers for the creation of decentralized, decarbonized, and democratized energy systems towards sustainable development[86,49]. The use of enabling technologies in REC can improve the energy supply chain by promoting efficiency and price affordability thereby minimizing costs. Such a system can lessen power outages and blackouts by providing decentralized local energy sources to the main utility provider. These technologies can promote the proliferation of prosumers, resulting in lower electricity costs and improved distribution of electricity. According to the reports from Deloitte and IRENA, the operation of the energy market based on DLT such as blockchain is more efficient and transparent, which can improve market competition and promote the adaptation of energy suppliers, as well as minimize operating costs, achieving rapid and automated processing[29,43]. This finding is supported by BIS which stated that the value of DLT applications across the energy market in 2018 was valued to 518.6 million US dollars, and it's projected to be about 6.29 billion US dollars in 2024[17].

According to Deloitte DLT has the capability to disrupt energy-related products and services which can be interoperable traded as digital assets[56]. As such the application of DLT in the energy sector is considered as a valuable technology for attaining sustainable energy in REC[79]. Overall, the use of DLT based smart contracts, IoT and AI can support decentralized energy trading and electricity supply, effective and automated control and secure of energy storage in REC[49]. The prosumer can be connected to the community grid via the DLT and smart contracts which ensures that data security and privacy concerns are reinforced for safe energy sharing transaction in REC. Besides, a fair energy pricing policy is essential for improving energy sharing and trading

services in REC. As such, this study suggests the deployment of a smart contracts to enable decentralized trading for REC. The use of IoT devices can lessen the need for human resources by supporting AI based algorithms that provides intelligent energy systems that predicts energy needs to meet short term energy demand, monitoring, and managing of the entire energy supply and demand. IoT devices such as energy metering devices provides real-time energy demand and supply data for AI and DLT based systems for P2P energy sharing to help in managing RES production and consumption in REC.

Research implications

In REC, new business models, regulations, flexible solutions, and technologies are to be developed for data driven energy management towards facilitating optimal energy demand and supply. Specifically, energy sharing and tracking, as an essential constituent for sustainable energy management, is experiencing an advancement from centralized to distributed approaches[84]. The use of enabling technologies can accelerate the global energy transformation[79]. Necessitating the need for enabling technologies for achieving a decentralized energy as a service ecosystem[9]. DLT can enable seamless integration with legacy system enabling the scaling up of energy[70]. The adoption of DLT provide the infrastructure for creating open, immutable, and secure markets for matching of energy demand and supply at local level, enabling prosumers to transfer their self-produced energy into the micro grid to be shared and traded with consumers[71,79]. The deployment of smart contracts can aid the settlement of imbalances within the electricity markets, as well as tracking the source of energy supplied to consumers in real-time[66]. Therefore, this current study contributes to the body of knowledge by holistically exploring and conceptualizing the adoption of enabling technologies to improve energy sharing and tracking in REC to offer research implications for academic research as well as institutional development. However, the application of these enabling technologies is influenced by key factors that impacts specific energy use cases. Grounded on secondary data a conceptual model is designed that identifies the factors that impacts the adoption of enabling technologies in REC.

Practical implications

This study aims to contribute to research on REC by designing an approach that support energy sharing and tracing by adopting enabling technologies (DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI) to enable a trusted and decentralized energy trading and sharing approach. Moreover, findings from this article suggest that the developed approach (as seen in Fig. 4), provides data for generation, controlling, and scheduling of RES in a distributed manner to meet the community grid's load demand. The model can help to manage the distributed energy and data flow among transacting actors in a credible manner that enables energy prosumers and consumers to track the generation and trading of energy in a distinctive transaction. In the designed approach IoT devices such as advanced metering infrastructure and automated meter reading technology generates real-time data that are processed by AI based machine learning which are saved in the distributed ledger employed by smart contracts to tracing back the source of each kilowatt-hour of electricity supplied [19]. In this research, AI based machine learning analyze energy data from IoT devices to make intelligent decision for demand side energy management for data digitization, profiling short-term and long-term load forecasting, resource management, energy storage facilitation, and system failure prediction, and prevention. Using smart contracts, the designed approach provides transparent, open, tamper-proof energy sharing for self-procuring and trading and tracking operation of renewable energy supply. The developed approach employs a P2P energy sharing approach that employs enabling technologies to manage inter-connected microgrids that maintains RES production from prosumers to consumers in a more secure, transparent, and distributed

manner. This contributes to lessen energy charges, promote green energy consumption, and give incentives to prosumers for participating in energy sharing in REC.

Conclusion

Global climate change, decarbonization, and access to renewable energy in rural communities is seen as one of the major issues in the last decade. Microgrids utilizing renewable energy resources offer a promising approach to mitigating these issues, and this can be facilitated by actualization of self-sufficient REC. To conclude, REC have the prospect to further develop P2P energy sharing to enhance sustainable production and consumption of renewable energy. Findings from this study suggest that DLT, AI, and IoT can accelerate renewable energy transition in REC. Evidence from this study discusses how AI, DLT based smart contracts and IoT help for orchestrating energy sharing and trading mechanism in REC, explores how DLT based smart contracts, IoT, and AI help to achieve sustainable tracking of RES in REC, and more importantly examines the key factors that influence the adoption of AI, DLT based smart contracts and IoT in REC. Hence, findings from this study suggest that the adoption of enabling technologies supports energy-efficient products and services in REC, by introducing innovative business models that could improve energy efficiency in the emerging economies. The adoption of enabling technologies have the potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, increasing access to affordable energy and empowering local communities

Limitations from this study includes the scope of the study is grounded on literature review of available sources related to REC. Another limitation is the reliance on only secondary data or the generalizability of the findings to different REC contexts. Lastly, the designed conceptual model for enabling technologies adoption in REC (as seen in Fig. 6) was not validated. For further work the designed conceptual model will be validated using data from empirical evidence and case studies collected from prosumers, consumers, and utility companies for REC in developing countries. Also, the proposed approach as seen in Fig. 4 will be further evaluated by utilizing real-time data from energy metering devices deployed by prosumers in REC. The produced dataset will comprise time-series electricity consumption (MW) data from a certain time period. Based on the time-series data, the date, and time of the energy consumption data will be used to extract hidden patterns to forecast short-term and long-term RES estimate for predictive analysis models using a bi-directional LSTM (bi-directional long, short-term memory) by assessing the Mean square error, R^2 score, root means square error, and mean absolute error.

For the DLT platform an open-source platform such as IOTA tangle or Hyperledger Fabric can be employed to develop the DApp which will comprise of a distributed network of peers and a hidden node running as an image in the container. The peers will consist of smart contract and data storage (e.g. CouchDB), to record energy related transactions to the distributed ledger in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format. Moreover, RESTful APIs will be deployed that enable distributed grid network services such as scheduling, pricing, V2G, G2V, V2X, etc. for energy consumer, prosumer, and utility operator. Lastly, based on the proposed application of DLT based smart contracts, IoT and AI (as seen in Fig. 4), for energy tracking future works will involve the development of a DLT, IoT, and AI based platform to be implemented for energy tracking. The platform will support to track energy from energy generation, energy transmission, energy transformation, electricity distribution, electricity consumption and energy sharing. The platform will be enabled by DLT based smart contracts to support electricity tracking operation and sharing mechanism in REC.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bokolo Anthony Jnr: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology,

Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank the anonymous reviewers, associate editor, and the editor-in-chief for their comments and recommendations. These have been valuable to improve prior versions of the manuscript.

References

- [1] B.O. Abisoye, Y. Sun, W. Zenghui, A survey of artificial intelligence methods for renewable energy forecasting: methodologies and insights, *Renew. Energy Focus* 100529 (2023).
- [2] L. Ableitner, A. Meeuw, S. Schopfer, V. Tiefenbeck, F. Wortmann, A. Wörner, Quartierstrom—implementation of a real world prosumer centric local energy market in Walenstadt, Switzerland, 2019. arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.07242.
- [3] A. Aderibole, A. Aljarwan, M.H.U. Rehman, H.H. Zeineldin, T. Mezher, K. Salah, D. Svetinovic, Blockchain technology for smart grids: decentralized NIST conceptual model, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 43177–43190.
- [4] A. Ahl, M. Yarime, K. Tanaka, D. Sagawa, Review of blockchain-based distributed energy: implications for institutional development, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 107 (2019) 200–211.
- [5] M. Aloqaily, A. Boukerche, O. Bouachir, F. Khalid, S. Jangsher, An energy trade framework using smart contracts: overview and challenges, *IEEE Netw.* 34 (4) (2020) 119–125.
- [6] C. Antal, T. Cioara, M. Antal, V. Mihailescu, D. Mitrea, I. Anghel, F. Bellesini, Blockchain based decentralized local energy flexibility market, *Energy Rep.* 7 (2021) 5269–5288.
- [7] B. Anthony Jnr, Applying enterprise architecture for digital transformation of electro mobility towards sustainable transportation, in: *Proceedings of the 2020 on Computers and People Research Conference*, 2020, pp. 38–46.
- [8] B. Anthony Jnr, Smart city data architecture for energy presumption in municipalities: concepts, requirements, and future directions, *Int. J. Green Energy* 17 (13) (2020) 827–845.
- [9] B. Anthony Jnr, Integrating electric vehicles to achieve sustainable energy as a service business model in smart cities, *Front. Sustain. Cities* 3 (2021) 685716.
- [10] B. Anthony Jnr, Developing green urban mobility policies for sustainable public transportation in local communities: a Norwegian perspective, *J. Place Manage. Dev.* 17 (1) (2024) 136–155.
- [11] B. Anthony Jnr, S. Abbas Petersen, D. Ahlers, J. Krogstie, API deployment for big data management towards sustainable energy presumption in smart cities—a layered architecture perspective, *Int. J. Sustain. Energ.* 39 (3) (2020) 263–289.
- [12] B. Anthony Jr, The role of community engagement in urban innovation towards the co-creation of smart sustainable cities, *J. Knowl. Econ.* (2023) 1–33.
- [13] B. Anthony, S.A. Petersen, D. Ahlers, J. Krogstie, K. Livik, Big data-oriented energy presumption service in smart community districts: a multi-case study perspective, *Energy Informat.* 2 (1) (2019) 1–26.
- [14] K. Ashton, That ‘internet of things’ thing, *RFID J.* 22 (7) (2009) 97–114.
- [15] N. Bakker, Energy Track & Trace using Blockchain, 2022. <https://ee-ip.org/en/article/energy-track-trace-using-blockchain-5951> (accessed on 27 November 2022).
- [16] J. Bao, D. He, M. Luo, K.K.R. Choo, A survey of blockchain applications in the energy sector, *IEEE Syst. J.* 15 (3) (2020) 3370–3381.
- [17] BIS, 2019. BIS Research Company-Analysis and forecast of global blockchain in the energy market 2018–2024. <https://bisresearch.com/industry-report/blockchain-in-energy-market.html>.
- [18] A.J. Bokolo, Examining the adoption of sustainable eMobility-sharing in smart communities: diffusion of innovation theory perspective, *Smart Cities* 6 (4) (2023) 2057–2080.
- [19] A. Bokolo Jnr, Examining the use of intelligent conversational voice-assistants for improved mobility behavior of older adults in smart cities, *Int. J. Human-Computer Interact.* (2024) 1–22.
- [20] Brooklyn Microgrid, LO3 Energy’s Brooklyn Microgrid project, 2019. <https://www.brooklyn.energy/> (accessed on 10 May 2024).
- [21] M.A. Buth, A.A. Wiczorek, G.G. Verbong, The promise of peer-to-peer trading? The potential impact of blockchain on the actor configuration in the Dutch electricity system, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 53 (2019) 194–205.
- [22] S.C.K. Chau, J. Xu, W. Bow, K. Elbassioni, Peer-to-peer energy sharing: effective cost-sharing mechanisms and social efficiency, in: *Proceedings of the Tenth ACM International Conference on Future Energy Systems*, 2019, pp. 215–225.

- [23] Y. Chen, C. Zhao, Review of energy sharing: business models, mechanisms, and prospects, *IET Renew. Power Gener.* 16 (12) (2022) 2468–2480.
- [24] Y. Chen, S. Mei, F. Zhou, S.H. Low, W. Wei, F. Liu, An energy sharing game with generalized demand bidding: model and properties, *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid* 11 (3) (2019) 2055–2066.
- [25] L. Cheng, T. Yu, A new generation of AI: a review and perspective on machine learning technologies applied to smart energy and electric power systems, *Int. J. Energy Res.* 43 (6) (2019) 1928–1973.
- [26] Cityxchange, 2019. +CityxChange (Positive City Exchange). <https://cityxchange.eu/about-cityxchange/> (accessed on 10 May 2024).
- [27] O. Corradi, How to trace back the origin of electricity, 2021. <https://www.electricitymaps.com/blog/flow-tracing> (accessed on 27 November 2022).
- [28] L. de Almeida, V. Cappelli, N. Klausmann, H. van Soest, Peer-to-peer trading and energy community in the electricity market: analysing the literature on law and regulation and looking ahead to future challenges. International Energy Agency (2021).
- [29] L.L.P. Deloitte, *Blockchain Enigma, Paradox. Opportunity*, The Creative Studio at Deloitte, London J, 2016, p. 7969.
- [30] M.L. Di Silvestre, P. Gallo, M.G. Ippolito, E.R. Sanseverino, G. Zizzo, A technical approach to the energy blockchain in microgrids, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inf.* 14 (11) (2018) 4792–4803.
- [31] X. Duan, Intelligent electricity purchase and sale trading platform based on blockchain, in: 2020 International Conference on Communications, Information System and Computer Engineering (CISCE). IEEE, 2020, pp. 183–189.
- [32] U. e Ammara, S.S. Zehra, S. Nazir, I. Ahmad, Artificial neural network-based nonlinear control and modeling of a DC microgrid incorporating regenerative FC/HPEV and energy storage system, *Renew. Energy Focus* 49 (2024) 100565.
- [33] EKOenergy, Tracking of energy. <https://www.ekoenergy.org/ecolabel/criteria/tracking/> (accessed on 27 November 2022), 2021.
- [34] H. El Hafdaoui, A. Khallaayoun, Internet of energy (IoE) adoption for a secure semi-decentralized renewable energy distribution, *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.* 57 (2023) 103307.
- [35] European Commission, 2023. Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub. https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/index_en. (accessed on 06 May 2024).
- [36] M.A. Ferrag, L. Maglaras, DeepCoin: A novel deep learning and blockchain-based energy exchange framework for smart grids, *IEEE Trans. Eng. Manage.* 67 (4) (2019) 1285–1297.
- [37] A. Fink, *Conducting research literature reviews: from the internet to paper*, Sage publications, 2019.
- [38] M. Galici, M. Mureddu, E. Ghiani, G. Celli, F. Pilo, P. Porcu, B. Canetto, Energy blockchain for public energy communities, *Appl. Sci.* 11 (8) (2021) 3457.
- [39] Goiener, Goiener-Renewable energy generation and consumption cooperative, 2018. <https://www.goiener.com/es/> (accessed on 10 May 2024).
- [40] L. Hall, Bitcoin Technology to Fuel P2P Solar Revolution?, WWW Document], 2016. URL. <https://understandsolar.com/bitcoin-technology-p2p-solar/>. (accessed on 18 November 2022).
- [41] W. Hua, Y. Chen, M. Qardran, J. Jiang, H. Sun, J. Wu, Applications of blockchain and artificial intelligence technologies for enabling prosumers in smart grids: a review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 161 (2022) 112308.
- [42] M.A. Husain, S.B. Pingale, A.B. Khan, A.F. Minai, Y. Pandey, R.S. Dwivedi, Performance analysis of the global maximum power point tracking based on spider monkey optimization for PV system, *Renew. Energy Focus* 47 (2023) 100503.
- [43] Irena, Innovation landscape for a renewable-powered future: solutions to integrate variable renewables, 2019.
- [44] R. Jain, A. Dogra, Solar energy distribution using blockchain and IoT integration, in: Proceedings of the 2019 International Electronics Communication Conference, 2019, pp. 118–123.
- [45] F. Jamil, N. Iqbal, S. Ahmad, D. Kim, Peer-to-peer energy trading mechanism based on blockchain and machine learning for sustainable electrical power supply in smart grid, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 39193–39217.
- [46] B.A. Jnr, Decentralized AIoT based intelligence for sustainable energy prosumption in local energy communities: a citizen-centric prosumer approach, *Cities* 152 (2024) 105198.
- [47] B.A. Jnr, Developing a decentralized community of practice-based model for on-demand electric car-pooling towards sustainable shared mobility, *Case Stud. Transp. Pol.* 15 (2024) 101136.
- [48] B.A. Jnr, S.A. Petersen, D. Ahlers, J. Krogstie, Big data driven multi-tier architecture for electric mobility as a service in smart cities: a design science approach, *Int. J. Energy Sect. Manage.* 14 (5) (2020) 1023–1047.
- [49] O. Juszczyk, K. Shahzad, Blockchain technology for renewable energy: principles, applications and prospects, *Energies* 15 (13) (2022) 4603.
- [50] A.A. Khan, A.A. Laghari, M. Rashid, H. Li, A.R. Javed, T.R. Gadekallu, Artificial intelligence and blockchain technology for secure smart grid and power distribution automation: a state-of-the-art review, *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.* 57 (2023) 103282.
- [51] M. Khorasany, Revolutionising track and trace in supply chain using Blockchain technology, 2021. <https://medium.com/tymlz/revolutionising-track-and-trace-in-supply-chain-using-blockchain-technology-20e5a9a07c65> (accessed on 27 November 2022).
- [52] B. Kitchenham, S. Charters, Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering. EBSE, Keele Univ., Newcastle, U.K., Tech. Rep. EBSE 2007-001, 2007, 2007, p. 1051.
- [53] R.K. Kodali, S. Yerroju, B.Y.K. Yogi, Blockchain based energy trading, in: TENCON 2018-2018 IEEE Region 10 Conference (pp. 1778–1783). IEEE, 2018.
- [54] X. Kong, H. Mu, H. Wang, N. Li, X. Liu, Two-layer optimization method for sharing energy storage and energy considering subjectivity. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 2024, 2024.
- [55] Z. Li, S. Bahramirad, A. Paaso, M. Yan, M. Shahidehpour, Blockchain for decentralized transactive energy management system in networked microgrids, *Electr. J.* 32 (4) (2019) 58–72.
- [56] C. Liu, X. Zhang, K.K. Chai, J. Loo, Y. Chen, A survey on blockchain-enabled smart grids: advances, applications and challenges, *IET Smart Cities* 3 (2) (2021) 56–78.
- [57] E. Mengelkamp, J. Gärtner, K. Rock, S. Kessler, L. Orsini, C. Weinhardt, Designing microgrid energy markets: a case study: The Brooklyn Microgrid, *Appl. Energy* 210 (2018) 870–880.
- [58] S.T. Meraj, S.S. Yu, M.S. Rahman, K. Hasan, M.H. Lipu, H. Trinh, Energy management schemes, challenges and impacts of emerging inverter technology for renewable energy integration towards grid decarbonization, *J. Clean. Prod.* 405 (2023) 137002.
- [59] F.D. Minuto, A. Lanzini, Energy-sharing mechanisms for energy community members under different asset ownership schemes and user demand profiles, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 168 (2022) 112859.
- [60] B. Morvaj, R. Evins, J. Carmeliet, Decarbonizing the electricity grid: The impact on urban energy systems, distribution grids and district heating potential, *Appl. Energy* 191 (2017) 125–140.
- [61] nrgcoin, 2022. NRGcoin - Smart Contract for green energy. <http://www.nrgcoin.org> (accessed on 24 November 2022).
- [62] S. Paiho, J. Kiljander, R. Sarala, H. Siikavirta, O. Kilkki, A. Bajpai, T. Weissaupt, Towards cross-commodity energy-sharing communities – a review of the market, regulatory, and technical situation, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 151 (2021) 111568.
- [63] I. Petri, M. Barati, Y. Rezgui, O.F. Rana, Blockchain for energy sharing and trading in distributed prosumer communities, *Comput. Ind.* 123 (2020) 103282.
- [64] A. Petrusic, A. Janjic, Renewable energy tracking and optimization in a hybrid electric vehicle charging station, *Appl. Sci.* 11 (1) (2020) 245.
- [65] L. Pires Klein, A. Krivoglazova, L. Matos, J. Landeck, M. De Azevedo, A novel peer-to-peer energy sharing business model for the Portuguese energy market, *Energies* 13 (1) (2019) 125.
- [66] C. Pop, M. Antal, T. Cioara, I. Anghel, D. Sera, I. Salomie, M. Bertoncini, Blockchain-based scalable and tamper-evident solution for registering energy data, *Sensors* 19 (14) (2019) 3033.
- [67] Powerledger, 2016. Powerledger's technology. <https://www.powerledger.io/company/about> (accessed on 10 May 2024).
- [68] Quartierstrom, Quartierstrom– P2P Prosumer Energy Village, 2020. <https://www.housingevolutions.eu/project/quartierstrom-p2p-prosumer-energy-village> (accessed on 10 May 2024).
- [69] M.S. Reza, M. Mannan, S.B. Wali, M.A. Hannan, K.P. Jern, S.A. Rahman, T. I. Mahlia, Energy storage integration towards achieving grid decarbonization: a bibliometric analysis and future directions, *J. Storage Mater.* 41 (2021) 102855.
- [70] M. Schletz, A. Cardoso, G. Prata Dias, S. Salomo, How can blockchain technology accelerate energy efficiency interventions? A use case comparison, *Energies* 13 (22) (2020) 5869.
- [71] A. Schneiders, D. Shipworth, Community energy groups: Can they shield consumers from the risks of using blockchain for peer-to-peer energy trading? *Energies* 14 (12) (2021) 3569.
- [72] S. Schusser, J. Jaraité, Explaining the interplay of three markets: Green certificates, carbon emissions and electricity, *Energy Econ.* 71 (2018) 1–13.
- [73] S. Seven, G. Yao, A. Soran, A. Onen, S.M. Mueyen, Peer-to-peer energy trading in virtual power plant based on blockchain smart contracts, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 175713–175726.
- [74] G. Sharma, A.M. Joshi, S.P. Mohanty, sTrade: Blockchain based secure energy trading using vehicle-to-grid mutual authentication in smart transportation, *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.* 57 (2023) 103296.
- [75] J. Sousa, J. Lagarto, C. Camus, C. Viveiros, F. Barata, P. Silva, O. Parafba, Renewable energy communities optimal design supported by an optimization model for investment in PV/wind capacity and renewable electricity sharing, *Energy* 283 (2023) 128464.
- [76] A. Srikanth, G.N.Y. Narayanan, S.K. Lakshmanan, H.V. Baskar, J. Jayaraman, V. Vijayaraghavan, Prosumer based economic model for energy sharing between microgrids in a rural Indian village scenario, in: 2020 IEEE Global Humanitarian Technology Conference (GHTC). IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [77] Sunchain, 2021. The Sunchain Solution. <http://www.Sunchain.fr> (accessed on 24 November 2022).
- [78] K. Tanaka, K. Nagakubo, R. Abe, Blockchain-based electricity trading with Digitalgrid router, in: IEEE international conference on consumer electronics-Taiwan (ICCE-TW), 2017, pp. 201–202.
- [79] F. Teng, Q. Zhang, G. Wang, J. Liu, H. Li, A comprehensive review of energy blockchain: application scenarios and development trends, *Int. J. Energy Res.* 45 (12) (2021) 17515–17531.
- [80] Y. Tian, G. Zeng, A. Rutt, T. Shi, H. Kim, J. Wang, G. Ceder, Promises and challenges of next-generation “beyond Li-ion” batteries for electric vehicles and grid decarbonization, *Chem. Rev.* 121 (3) (2020) 1623–1669.
- [81] P.K. Wan, L. Huang, Energy tracing and blockchain technology: a primary review, in: International Conference on Intelligent Technologies and Applications, 2022, pp. 223–231.
- [82] J. Wang, H. Zhong, J. Qin, W. Tang, R. Rajagopal, Q. Xia, C. Kang, Incentive mechanism for sharing distributed energy resources, *J. Mod Power Syst. Clean Energy* 7 (4) (2019) 837–850.

- [83] J. Wang, H. Zhong, C. Wu, E. Du, Q. Xia, C. Kang, Incentivizing distributed energy resource aggregation in energy and capacity markets: an energy sharing scheme and mechanism design, *Appl. Energy* 252 (2019) 113471.
- [84] N. Wang, X. Zhou, X. Lu, Z. Guan, L. Wu, X. Du, M. Guizani, When energy trading meets blockchain in electrical power system: the state of the art, *Appl. Sci.* 9 (8) (2019) 1561.
- [85] Q. Wang, M. Su, Integrating blockchain technology into the energy sector—from theory of blockchain to research and application of energy blockchain, *Comput. Sci. Rev.* 37 (2020) 100275.
- [86] Q. Wang, R. Li, L. Zhan, Blockchain technology in the energy sector: From basic research to real world applications, *Comput. Sci. Rev.* 39 (2021) 100362.
- [87] Y. Wang, Y. Cao, Y. Li, L. Jiang, Y. Long, Y. Deng, Y. Nakanishi, Modelling and analysis of a two-level incentive mechanism based peer-to-peer energy sharing community, *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* 133 (2021) 107202.
- [88] C. Wu, X. Chen, H. Hua, K. Yu, L. Gan, J. Shen, Y. Ding, Peer-to-peer energy trading optimization for community prosumers considering carbon cap-and-trade, *Appl. Energy* 358 (2024) 122611.
- [89] J. Wu, N.K. Tran, Application of blockchain technology in sustainable energy systems: an overview, *Sustainability* 10 (9) (2018) 3067.
- [90] Y. Xia, Q. Xu, F. Li, Grid-friendly pricing mechanism for peer-to-peer energy sharing market diffusion in communities, *Appl. Energy* 334 (2023) 120685.
- [91] A. Yagmur, B.A. Dedeturk, A. Soran, J. Jung, A. Onen, Blockchain-based energy applications: the DSO perspective, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 145605–145625.
- [92] Y. Yang, D. Peng, W. Wang, X. Zhang, Block-chain based Energy Tracing Method for Electric Vehicles Charging, in: 2020 IEEE Sustainable Power and Energy Conference (iSPEC), 2020, pp. 2622–2627.
- [93] A. Yildizbasi, Blockchain and renewable energy: integration challenges in circular economy era, *Renew. Energy* 176 (2021) 183–197.
- [94] C. Zhang, T. Yang, Y. Wang, Peer-to-peer energy trading in a microgrid based on iterative double auction and blockchain, *Sustain. Energy Grids Networks* 27 (2021) 100524.
- [95] Q. Zhang, T. Xu, D. Wang, Z. Liu, C. Cheng, S. Zheng, G. Wang, Study of traceability system of renewable energy power trading based on blockchain technology, in: 2022 International Conference on Blockchain Technology and Information Security (ICBCTIS), 2022, pp. 171–176.
- [96] Y. Zhou, P.D. Lund, Peer-to-peer energy sharing and trading of renewable energy in smart communities— trading pricing models, decision-making and agent-based collaboration, *Renew. Energy* 207 (2023) 177–193.